

Integrating the Virtual Reality Laboratory into the Educational Process
Интеграция лаборатории виртуальной реальности в образовательный процесс

Virtual reallik laboratoriyasini ta'lim jarayoniga integratsiya qilish
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Abstract. The article discusses the scientific and methodological aspects of using the virtual reality laboratory in the educational process. *The purpose of the study:* the study of the impact of virtual reality and virtual reality laboratories on education in universities. *Research objectives:* to analyze the use of virtual reality technology in education in general; to identify the relevance and analyze the statistics of the effectiveness of teaching using virtual reality laboratories in schools; to describe the main usefulness of using virtual reality laboratories in universities; to demonstrate the experience of using a virtual reality laboratory in Universities.

Keywords: virtual reality; virtual reality laboratory; modern technologies; system; educational process.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются научно-методические аспекты использования лаборатории виртуальной реальности в образовательном процессе. Цель исследования: изучение влияния виртуальной реальности и лабораторий виртуальной реальности на образование в вузах. Задачи исследования: проанализировать использование технологий виртуальной реальности в образовании в целом; выявить актуальность и проанализировать статистику эффективности обучения с использованием лабораторий виртуальной реальности в школах; описать основные преимущества использования лабораторий виртуальной реальности в вузах; продемонстрировать опыт использования лаборатории виртуальной реальности в университетах.

Ключевые слова: виртуальная реальность; лаборатория виртуальной реальности; современные технологии; система; образовательный процесс.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada ta'lim jarayonida virtual reallik laboratoriyasidan foydalanishning ilmiy va uslubiy jihatlari muhokama qilinib, o'rganilgan. Tadqiqotning maqsadi: maktab va universitetlarda ta'lim jarayoniga virtual reallik va virtual reallik laboratoriyalarining ta'sirini o'rganish. Tadqiqot vazifalari: umuman olganda ta'limda virtual reallik texnologiyasidan foydalanishni tahlil qilish; maktablarda virtual reallik laboratoriyalaridan foydalanish samaradorligi bo'yicha dolzarblik va statistik ma'lumotlarni aniqlash hamda tahlil qilish; universitetlarda virtual reallik laboratoriyalaridan foydalanishning asosiy foydali jihatlarni tavsiflash; Oliy ta'limda virtual reallik laboratoriyasidan foydalanish tajribasini namoyish etish.

Kalit so'zlar: virtual reallik; virtual reallik laboratoriyasi; zamonaviy texnologiyalar; tizim; ta'lim jarayoni.

Introduction

Today's society is developing in ways that require innovative approaches. In Uzbekistan, innovation has been declared a key priority of economic policy. The government is actively working to create institutions that support this area.

To enhance the quality of the educational process, it is necessary to introduce innovative technologies that will increase the efficiency of learning and engage the younger generation. At present, innovations are intended to stabilize the educational process and align societal demands with the individual needs of each person. Virtual reality is one of the innovative technologies that has begun to gain popularity in the field of education [1–4]. Virtual reality is a technology that creates a virtual environment into which a person is placed. Immersion into this environment occurs through the use of headsets, headphones, joysticks, and other devices. Within virtual reality, it is possible to interact with surrounding objects (for example, a user can pick up a nearby item and throw it).

Research Methods

The application of virtual reality opens up new opportunities in education, enabling teachers and students to safely conduct physical and chemical experiments, thereby diversifying the learning process in physics and chemistry classes. It also allows learners to travel across different historical periods, with teachers providing students the opportunity to immerse themselves in past events and their atmosphere, explore planets during astronomy lessons, and much more—both within formal and supplementary education.

Learning with the use of virtual reality helps eliminate distractions, allowing students to become fully immersed in the educational process. Virtual reality also broadens the scope of communication by enabling the invitation of various scientists, historical figures, and renowned personalities from different fields to participate in lessons. What was once considered science fiction or fantasy has now become a reality actively used by people today.

Studying certain subjects requires not only lecture-based material but also hands-on experiential interaction. VR technologies make it possible to achieve this integration of theory and practice.

Research Results

Virtual reality laboratories in schools provide a new perspective on conducting laboratory work. For example, using the VR Chemistry Lab software, students can perform chemistry experiments involving toxic substances, concentrated acids and alkalis, flammable liquids, and heating devices. This significantly minimizes the risks for both students and teachers when working with hazardous materials, while still allowing learners to consolidate theoretical knowledge through practical virtual experiments.

Statistical data demonstrate that students engaged in lessons incorporating virtual reality laboratories show higher learning efficiency compared to those in traditional settings. This is primarily due to the fact that students remain focused on

the learning process, which is presented in an innovative, technology-driven, and creative manner.

It is also crucial to recognize that university students must acquire practical experience that will enable them to become professionals in their respective fields. Today, thanks to virtual reality technologies, medical students are able to engage in practical training through VR laboratories that simulate complex surgical operations. Such training allows them to memorize and practice step-by-step algorithms of medical procedures.

At Samarkand State University (SamSU), a virtual reality laboratory has been established, equipped with VR headsets and omnidirectional treadmills for movement within virtual environments. The university currently hosts master classes demonstrating the potential of virtual reality and its application in education. Additionally, courses on VR application development for various educational domains are conducted. Every second Saturday of the month, the university holds an open day, during which prospective students can become acquainted with VR technologies, accompanied by lectures on the use of VR in education.

The laboratory staff also provide training for both students and educators on the implementation of virtual reality in education. A wide range of VR-supported educational programs are offered, systematically organized by subject area and field of application.

Furthermore, virtual reality laboratories can offer a unique experience for students with physical disabilities. Through VR technologies, children are able to experience full freedom of movement in a virtual environment, remain under the constant supervision of instructors, and gain extraordinary emotions while exploring virtual worlds.

Conclusion

The technology employed in virtual reality laboratories is regarded as a unique tool that enables learners, including those with disabilities, to develop social interaction skills within individually tailored virtual environments. This, in turn, prepares them for future engagement in professional settings, companies, and collaborative teams.

References

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